

ROLE OF INTERACTIVE READING ACTIVITIES IN ESL CLASSROOMS

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Abstract Researchers and educators have focused on reading comprehension for a long time, but many students still struggle to comprehend the text. In this sense, this study examines how pre-, during-, and post-reading activities improve students' reading comprehension. The research focuses on reading class activities. The researcher used a series of student-centred reading activities to study reading processes. In reading class, the data was gathered through reading comprehension activities. The study included a number of different universities' students. The findings demonstrate that the pre-, during-, and post-reading activities are effective in developing students' reading skills.

In this article, we are also going to talk about various fun reading activities for an ESL classroom, so both classroom and online English teachers can learn new ways to engage with their students.

Key words: comprehension, struggle, sense, student-centered, pre-, during, and post-reading, ESL classroom.

Introduction

The most crucial skill in language is reading [1]. In this sense, teachers play a crucial role in improving students' reading comprehension. Teachers in reading classes use reading activities and strategies to accomplish this. In light of this discussion, perusing cognizance can be accomplished through perusing exercises in understanding guidance. Perusing exercises assume a significant part in perusing

perception for making and constructing the importance in composed text. In order to improve students' reading comprehension, numerous researchers emphasize pre-, during-, and post-reading activities [2]. In order to evaluate, examine, and check students' comprehension while they are reading a written text, stimulating reading activities will be used in reading class as part of this study's attempt to examine the role of reading activities in reading comprehension. Good readers make sense of text, and if teachers work to improve reading comprehension, students will become active, purposeful readers who can control their own reading comprehension.

Reading is the most stable skill for learning a second language [1]. To put it another way, reading is the most important skill for learning a new language; to further develop language obtaining, perusers or understudies translate the text and attempt to comprehend essayist's message, in this sense sentence structure and jargon are significant variables for figuring out the perusing sections [1]. Researchers today believe that there are numerous essential factors for interpreting written text [2]. For many years, educators believed that the reason students have difficulty understanding the text was due to poor grammar and limited vocabulary. This is the conventional view of reading and reading instruction [3], in which teachers concentrate solely on grammar and vocabulary during the reading process. Teachers should use activities and strategies to help students understand what they are reading, so teachers should look over their instructions and figure out which activities help students understand what they are reading [2]. For many decades, researchers have focused on the process and nature of reading [4]. Reading skill can be taught in a variety of ways by language educators. In perusing exercises educators ought to zero in on peruser's understanding of text and educators ought to forestall unfortunate comprehension in perusing process [5]. Activities for reading are broken down into three stages: pre-reading, reading, and post-reading [6].

They are connected with each other yet every one of these stages has its own property [2]. There are three ways students can put their knowledge to use [5]. Action readers are ready to read a text, make sense of it, and learn new ideas,

concepts, and perspectives during the reading process in three stages [7]. Teachers should teach students to be effective and active readers in the target language in three stages: they should design student-centered reading activities that help students improve their reading comprehension and ability; Teachers in reading classes should take *the pre-reading, reading, and post-reading stages* into consideration when planning student-centered activities [8].

The reader's knowledge and experience are the focus of **the pre-reading stage**. to bring the reader's previous knowledge and experience to life; analysts give significance particularly pre perusing stage [9]. Through prereading activities, teachers introduce the subject matter in the prereading phase. Pre-reading activities have the potential to activate students' prior knowledge and background, allowing them to acquire new information and construct meaning from the target reading text [7]. Teachers build and activate background knowledge during the pre-reading phase, according to a general consensus [10]. Pre-perusing undertakings concentrate to a text and understudies make expectations on the text content by activating their earlier information in this sense pre perusing activities are connected with foundation information and educators can assemble new information and actuate background information through pre perusing exercises [3]. In other words, the pre-reading stage increases readers' interest and motivation, allowing teachers to activate students' background knowledge in the target text [6]. This stage breaks readers' barriers and allows readers to engage in reading. Students can prepare for the reading text by engaging in pre-reading activities based on this discussion. The pre-reading stage relies on students' prior knowledge, language proficiency, and motivation [10].

During the stage of **reading**; understudies can foster understanding procedures and attempt to interpret and grasp dangerous text entries; this stage centers around text however pre perusing stage centers around understudies' thoughts prior to perusing [9]. During the reading stage, teachers may emphasize the functions of unknown words, analyzing reference words, grammatical functions of sentences, and effective dictionary use; Lale also stated that reading helped her

improve her vocabulary, highlighting the significance of reading [11]. While the reading stage focuses on the structure and organization of the reading passage, it also focuses on the text's content, including both general and specific information [8].

In the post-reading stage, teachers can assess students' comprehension and conduct a more in-depth text analysis [9]. Students can use language that is related to the subject at this stage [12]. Students are able to use prior knowledge from the pre- and during-reading stages, evaluate, synthesize, and analyze the written text, and they are able to ask critical questions for constructing the meaning in the text in the post-reading stage [6]. Through these three phases understudies background information can be enacted by the educators; Students can use reading strategies to gain critical thinking skills for understanding the text while reading [4]. Speaking, writing, and listening skills can be combined with reading skills in a suitable manner. It is possible to mention that pre-reading activities focus on the text and allow students to make predictions about the content of the text based on their prior knowledge. Reading activities focus on decoding skills, and post-reading activities focus on discussing and analyzing the content of the text, both of which are related to comprehension of the text [2]. Students acquire reading comprehension and thinking skills during these three stages [13]. In this research paper, the researcher introduces key words and concepts using the brainstorming technique to activate students' prior knowledge. While generating topic-related ideas, students develop their cognitive abilities and generate new ideas and opinions [14]. The researcher also uses activities for previewing and predicting during the pre-reading stage; In this activity, students read the first and last paragraphs, look at the title, headings, and pictures; and students use their prior knowledge and familiarize themselves with the subject before reading [15]. Paraphrasing activities are used in this study to help students at the reading stage make predictions, use context or guess, and break words down into their component parts.

ESL Reading Puzzle

For this comprehension activity, you will need two jigsaw puzzles consisting of around 20 pieces each. You will need only the backs of those puzzles to write one word of a small story per each piece. However, you can try and search for blank puzzles, or create your own puzzle – whatever suits you best. Mix up the pieces of one of the puzzles and tell the students to assemble the story and then read it aloud. Use the second puzzle as an example of the correct story.

Rhyming Riddles

Prepare a worksheet with riddles that the students should read in order to figure out the mystery word. The clues include words that rhyme with the mystery word.

Scrambled Sentences

Write or print a text or a dialogue on a paper and then cut it into strips with one sentence per strip. Ask the students to assemble the sentences into coherent text or dialogue. For this reading comprehension activity, students can work in teams and the winning team should be the first to put the sentences together. To make the task more difficult, cut out words instead of sentences.

Filling in the Gaps

Ask students to fill in the gaps in a text with a word that passes best. You can suggest the three variants of words, whereas advanced students can come up with a missing word themselves, or even fill in the entire missing sentences.

Text Related Questions

In this reading comprehension activity, the students should read the text and answer the multiple-choice or true/false questions that are related to this text. Please note that the correct option should not be very obvious.

Book Discussion

Assign your students a book that they should read at home and then discuss the chapters during the class. The difficulty level of the book should correspond with the level of your students.

Proverbs and Idioms

Study the English proverbs and idioms together with your students and encourage them to find the matching proverbs and idioms in their mother tongue. If a proverb or idiom has the same meaning in the student's mother tongue but is explained by different words, encourage this student to translate this proverb or idiom into English. This activity will go a long way with reading comprehension.

Matching Comprehension Activities

Give your students a set of book descriptions accompanied by short biographies of fictional characters with a focus on their reading tastes. The task of the students is to match the readers with the books that would fit them best. Some books have similar topics, so the students have to read all descriptions very carefully in order not to be misled. For example, a person enjoys cooking and would like to buy a cookbook, but not a fiction book about cooking. You can replace the book descriptions with music albums, concerts, job descriptions – whatever you find useful for your students – and adjust the characters' bios accordingly. You can also match the job descriptions to jobs, headings to text, or use something else for this matching reading ESL activity.

Closest Meaning

Give your students a set of sentences and ask them to identify a sentence that is closest in meaning to the "main" sentence.

Irrelevant Sentences

Give your students several texts where one sentence is irrelevant and encourage them to identify this sentence. The students can work in teams, and the winning team should identify all irrelevant sentences earlier than other teams.

Dialogue Completion

During this ESL reading comprehension activity, you should ask your students to fill in the gaps in dialogues with the most suitable phrases.

Spelling Mistakes

Advanced students can try to identify the misspelled words in ESL readings.

Text Genre Identification

During this ESL reading activity, you should give your students several texts of different genres and encourage them to guess the genre.

In addition to reading skills themselves, such classroom reading games help the learners build up the following skills:

- sequencing
- summarizing
- comparing
- drawing conclusions
- solving problems
- finding the main idea, important facts, and supporting details

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